

CASE REPORT

A crime has occurred in an optics laboratory. There are no witnesses, no working cameras... only 4 lenses that appear to belong to the victim and the murderer, a fingerprint, a letter, and a few other objects.

You have been summoned as experts in forensic optics. Through a series of experiments with lenses, you must analyze the evidence and rule out suspects until you solve the case.

At the end of each correctly completed experiment, you will receive a clue that helps you get closer to discovering who the victim is and who the murderer is.

⚠ But be careful... each misinterpreted clue can lead you to the wrong conclusion, and time is running out. Will you be able to solve the mystery before the culprit disappears forever?

Forensic Science Police Department**Case No.: 2024-187****Officer in charge: Inspector Marta Rivas**

On 03/04/2025 at 18:00, a call was received alerting authorities to a possible crime at the Advanced Optics Laboratory. Upon arrival, officers found the scene in complete disarray, with clear signs of a violent struggle.

Despite the evidence collected, neither the victim nor the aggressor has been identified so far. All laboratory employees have been placed under investigation. The evidence suggests that both the victim and the perpetrator, both laboratory workers, have refractive errors and wore glasses, but their identities could not be determined due to the lack of witnesses.

2. EVIDENCE FOUND AT THE SCENE

- ◆ Several broken lenses from different pairs of glasses
- ◆ A fingerprint
- ◆ A human eyeball (pending confirmation)
- ◆ A handwritten letter with an encrypted message
- ◆ Damaged optical instruments and signs of a struggle
- ◆ Security cameras turned off on the night of the crime

3. INITIAL HYPOTHESES

- 🔍 The victim and the murderer are laboratory workers.
- 🔍 The victim and the murderer wear corrective lenses, according to the remains found.

Currently, the case remains open. Further analysis is required to determine the identity of the victim and the aggressor.

Handwritten signature of Inspector Marta Rivas.

Inspector Marta Rivas

CHALLENGE 1: Investigating the lenses at the crime scene

We are asked to perform a qualitative analysis of the lenses found to rule out options and find key clues. Identify the characteristics of the 4 available lenses.

	Draw the lens and the ray paths	Is the image magnified or reduced?	TYPE OF LENS a) Diverging b) Converging c) Neutral	Drawing of the thin lens indicating the position of its focal points
A				
B				
C				
D				

To obtain the clue, order the lenses according to their optical power, from the most negative to the most positive.

CLUE 1: IT HAS BEEN DISCOVERED THAT THE MOST NEGATIVE LENS DOES NOT BELONG TO EITHER THE VICTIM OR THE MURDERER; IT COMES FROM AN OPTICAL INSTRUMENT.

CHALLENGE 2: Imagen Formation

We need to obtain information about the remaining three lenses. To determine their power, you must perform a setup on the optical bench. The procedure is as follows:

- 1) Place the light source so that it back-illuminates the object.
- 2) Use a cylindrical holder to position the lens to the right of the light source.
- 3) Place the screen so that you can observe image formation.

1° Place the **MOST POWERFUL CONVERGING** lens between the object and the screen. The object distance must be -10 cm. Move the screen until you find the distance at which the image forms.

- Does an image form?
- Is the image real or virtual?

Draw the thin lens, the object, the image, and the path of the refracted rays.

2° Change the lens and place the **LEAST POWERFUL CONVERGING** lens between the object and the screen with an object distance of -20 cm. Move the screen until you find the image distance.

- Does an image form?
- Is the image real or virtual?

3° Repeat the process with the **DIVERGING** lens.

- Does an image form?
- Is the image real or virtual?
- Using only this diverging lens, could you obtain a real image on the screen?

CLUE 2: THE POLICE HAVE PROVIDED THE NAMES, PHOTOS, AND AGES OF ALL THE LABORATORY WORKERS.

CHALLENGE 3: Unlocking lens power

Assuming the lenses are thin, calculate using the “Gaussian lens formula” the optical power of each positive lens, knowing the object distance (s) and the image distance (s') on the optical bench.

LENS	Draw the thin lens, object, and image, indicating object distance (s) and image distance (s')	s	s'	f'	P' (D)
High Converging					
Low Converging					
Diverging					

$$\frac{1}{s'} - \frac{1}{s} = \frac{1}{f'}$$

$$P' (D) = \frac{1}{f' (m)}$$

CLUE 3: THE LIST OF REFRACTIVE ERRORS (AMETROPIAS) OF THE WORKERS.

CHALLENGE 4: Can all converging lenses be trusted?

Is the following statement true or false? *A positive/converging lens always forms a real image.*

Answer:

Check the following cases on the optical bench and with ray tracing using the most positive lens:

- A) Object farther than the object focal distance (f)
- B) Object closer than the object focal distance (f)
- C) Object at the object focal point (F)

	ON THE OPTICAL BENCH Circle the correct image characteristics.	WITH RAY TRACING - The thin lens and its focal points - The ray parallel to the optical axis that exits passing through F' - The ray that passes through F and exits parallel to the optical axis
A	REAL / VIRTUAL UPRIGHT / INVERTED MAGNIFIED / REDUCED	
B	REAL / VIRTUAL UPRIGHT / INVERTED MAGNIFIED / REDUCED	
C	REAL / VIRTUAL UPRIGHT / INVERTED MAGNIFIED / REDUCED	

CLUE 4: A TEXT WRITTEN BY THE VICTIM HAS BEEN FOUND AT THE CRIME SCENE.

CHALLENGE 5: The victim's secret message

1° A message written by the victim has been found containing a key clue about the identity of the murderer. However, the text appears inverted. Use one of the lenses to read the letter, as it contains crucial information about the possible victim and murderer.

- Which lens did you use?
- Is the image real or virtual?
- Is it upright or inverted relative to the original object?
- Is it larger or smaller than the object?

2° Replace the object with one shaped like a capital letter E. Reflect on the relationship between object position and image position, and object size and image size. Calculate the lateral magnification (M) of this lens as the ratio of image distances and the ratio of image and object sizes for a case where the object is well away from the object focal point.

$$M = \frac{s'}{s} = \frac{y'}{y}$$

	s	s'	M	y	y'	M
CASE 1	- 14 cm					

3° What do the sign and value of M indicate in each case?

4° Is it exactly the same magnification when calculated using distance ratios and size ratios? What might the differences be due to?

5° If the object distance is greater, will the lateral magnification be the same? Calculate the lateral magnification for other object distances. Has the image size changed?

	s	s'	M	y	y'	M
CASE 2	-15 cm					
CASE 3	-21 cm					

6° Adjust the object distance until you obtain $M = -1$. Is it possible?

CLUE 5: A FINGERPRINT HAS BEEN FOUND AT THE CRIME SCENE, AND IT IS KNOWN TO BELONG TO THE MURDERER.

CHALLENGE 6: The murderer's fingerprint

During the analysis of the fingerprint found at the crime scene, police identified a transverse fissure characteristic of workers who handle glass lenses. It has been determined that this fingerprint belongs to the murderer.

To observe it magnified and in detail:

- 1° Place the fingerprint on the optical bench holder and verify it is properly back-illuminated.
- 2° Separate the light source from the fingerprint by 2 cm.
- 3° Place the lens you consider most appropriate to generate a magnified real image that allows precise examination of the mark and confirmation of the perpetrator's identity.

CLUE 6: THE VICTIM'S EYE HAS BEEN RECOVERED IN GOOD CONDITION AND MUST BE ANALYZED TOGETHER WITH THE FORENSIC REPORT.

CHALLENGE 7: The victim's vision

An eyeball was found at the scene, which due to its physical and anatomical characteristics, it is presumed to belong to the victim. Due to the absence of other physical evidence, its study is requested to determine its refractive defect and provide relevant data for identifying the victim. To diagnose eye refraction, consider where the image of an object located at a very large distance (ideally infinity) is formed.

- **Emmetropic:** An emmetropic eye has clear vision because the image of an object at infinity forms on the retina.
- **Myopic:** The image of an object at infinity does NOT form on the retina, but in front of it. Corrected with a diverging (negative) lens.
- **Hyperopic:** The image of an object at infinity does NOT form on the retina, but behind it. Corrected with a converging (positive) lens.

1° To analyze the victim's eye refraction, rays must reach the eye from infinity. To do this, place the object (the E) at the OBJECT FOCAL POINT (F) of the MOST POSITIVE lens. When the object is at the focal point, rays exit parallel to the optical axis, producing an image at infinity. This process is called beam collimation. Do you find any distance at which an image forms? Verify experimentally.

2° Place the victim's eye to the right of the lens about +5 cm from it and observe where the image forms. Does the image form on the retina? Using an auxiliary screen, determine whether the eye is emmetropic, myopic, or hyperopic.

3° Turn off the back-illumination of the object and consider which remaining lens will compensate the victim's eye, the negative or the positive one. Once you have decided, place the lens in front of the eye and turn on the light to verify whether your deduction was correct.

REPORT FOR THE POLICE

NAME OF THE VICTIM: _____

NAME OF THE MURDERER: _____

Team signature:

CONFIDENTIAL

Thank you for your collaboration in solving the case. After the investigation, we confirm that the murderer is Clara Vélez, head of the laboratory, and the victim is Valeria Montes.

Valeria had developed a new intraocular lens for post-cataract surgery animals, called *OptiVet*, and implanted it in her own eye to test its effectiveness. Clara, fearing that Valeria would take all the credit for the discovery and innovation, decided to eliminate her. In an act of desperation, Clara removed Valeria's eye to study the lens and ensure that the project would not fall into her colleague's hands.

Thank you again for your help. The case is closed.

Sincerely,
The Police

CONFIDENTIAL

CLUE 2: LABORATORY WORKERS

Claire Williams, 39

Emily Johnson, 35

Olivia Parker, 39

Savannah Brooks, 32

Hannah Miller, 33

Ethan Carter, 34

Abigail Thompson, 30

Jacob Anderson, 29

Madison Clark, 61

Avery Collins, 36

Liam Bennett, 39

Chloe Harrison, 38

Michael Davis, 39

Christopher Wilson, 54

Jason Lee, 39

Verónica Cueva, 43

CLUE 3 : WORKERS' AMETROPIAS

WORKER	PUPIL	AXIAL LENGTH	AMETROPIA	PRESCRIPTION
Claire Williams	3.5	24.0	Hyperopic	+10.50 D
Emily Johnson	4.2	24.2	Myopic	-5.00 D
Olivia Parker	3.5	23.5	Myopic	-4.00 D
Savannah Brooks	3.8	22.5	Hyperopic	+10.50 D
Hannah Miller	4.2	25.5	Myopic	-4.00 D
Ethan Carter	3.6	25.0	Myopic	-4.00 D
Abigail Thompson	3.7	24.0	Myopic	-3.50 D
Jacob Anderson	4.8	27.0	Myopic	-4.00 D
Madison Clark	3.9	23.0	Hyperopic	+10.50 D
Avery Collins	4.3	25.0	Hyperopic	+4.50 D
Liam Bennett	3.5	24.0	Emmetropic	+0.00 D
Chloe Harrison	4.0	22.8	Myopic	-2.25 D
Michael Davis	4.4	26.0	Emmetropic	+0.00 D
Christopher Wilson	3.9	24.5	Emmetropic	+0.00 D
Jason Lee	3.7	23.5	Hyperopic	+10.50 D
Verónica Cueva	4.6	26.2	Hyperopic	+5.00 D

CLUE 5: FINGERPRINTS

Claire Williams

Emily Johnson

Olivia Parker

Savannah Brooks

Hannah Miller

Ethan Carter

Abigail Thompson

Jacob Anderson

Madison Clark

Avery Collins

Liam Bennett

Chloe Harrison

Michael Davis

Christopher Wilson

Jason Lee

Verónica Cueva

